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The Effects of Social Media to Enhance Employees' Intention in Organizations in Vietnam: Through Motivation, Knowledge Management and Employees' Performance

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate how social media (SM) effects on organizational employees' motivation, knowledge management (KM), employees' performance (EP) and how does these effects on employees' intention. A theoretical model is integrating with the help of Self-determination (motivational) theory through KM, EP and employees' intention. A questionnaire-based study was designed to test the aforementioned model. The quantitative data (n=349) is collected from different organization of Vietnam and analyzed through Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling. The results indicated that SM has positive and significant effect on employees' motivation, KM and their intention. However, this has not significance effect on their performance. Additionally, all the factors' moderating effects are positive and significant. The findings have some theoretical enlightenment and practical implications.

Originality: This is one of the few studies, which investigate the interrelationships among SM, KM, employees' performance on their intention and the first to test the model with self-determination theory factors on organizations in Vietnam.

Keywords

Social Media, Motivation, Knowledge Management; Employees' Performance.

1. Introduction

The Corona Virus pandemic (COVID-19) has a major influence on every area of the global economy (1) as well had the greatest impact on businesses. Because, of the corona outbreak, community movements and the number of employees working from home and the stay-at-home movement were restricted. The COVID-19 epidemic prompted the government to recommend social detachment in order to limit illness transmission by

reducing contact with others. The influence of social distancing creates a bad impact in operations and marketing is significant (2). Small businesses in Vietnam are forced to employ an online or SM based approach in critical times due to social alienation. Businesses and organizations can still do business through SM.

Rapid growth of Web 2.0 technology, SM has influence almost every aspect of peoples' life. Particularly in current years SM has becoming a necessary element of people's everyday life and a prevailing tool of increasing and maintaining relationships (3). SM breaks the limitation of space, time and allowing individuals with others anytime, anyplace; same time this makes communication convenient and makes peoples' life more social and colorful and providing users diverse alternatives for connecting with friends or strangers. Moreover, other peoples relying on SM, because of frequent advantageous and detrimental results of people's physio-psychological life (4).

To assists internal communication, learn and share knowledge between organizations and their employees are more dependent on the ever-changing and ever-expanding SM tools (5). The word SM is defined as a set of technologies, which allows users to simply, generate, change, and evaluate links to content or to connect with others creators through internet (6). These generally include with applications, as example blogs, social tagging systems, wikis, social bookmarking systems, micro-blogs, and social networking systems. In organizations SM are using to supporting social networking within the organization where only organizational users can access these systems to posting notes, informing and updating status, searching for materials, peoples or topics, visualizing social networks and signifying relations(7). According to Thomas and Akdere, (2013) in organizations SM practice has significant effects on different occupational interrelated effects, with KM and learning for workplace to increase EP (5). On the other hand Andriole, (2010) (8) stated, to utilize Web 2.0 KM is one of the most significant motives to deployment of SM. Organizations are paying additional attention in knowing how the social and mutual dimensions of SM could influence to support the conventional KM activities (9). Knowledge acquisition, creation, and sharing are the most important KM processes (10). Organizational learning can improved directly or indirectly through SM procedures, which support knowledge behaviors.

In recent studies research on SM most researchers are paying attention in linking the relationship among SM and KM, this may develop organizational knowledge through SM with organizational social culture (11). Despite that, employees' intention to use SM in the organization remains controversial, because of having the reputation of reducing productivity and increasing disturbance in organization. Not only that very few research are conduct with KM and EP (12, 13). There are some other factors exists which may influence in organizational performance, where motivation in one of them. Research on SM with motivation, KM and EP yet to very little for developing countries, spatially for Vietnam employees hard to find. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to investigate the interrelationships among SM, motivation, KM, and EP on their intention. This study also aims to studying the mediating role of motivation, KM and EP

between SM and employees' intention. Therefore, the main goals of this study were, (a) examine the relationship among the SM, motivation, KM and EP in the organization where represented in KM process and EP and (b) test the mediating role of motivation, KM, and EP as instrumental and enabling factors between the organizations' employees in the organizations of Vietnam.

This paper begins with the significant literature regarding with earlier studies with SM, KM, EP and the intention of the employees. Once these concepts been laid out, hypotheses are developed and tested. Clarifying the research approach following that. The findings of the study are then given. Discussions of research implications, constraints, and future study prospects are also addressed later on in the paper. Finally, a brief conclusion was offered.

2. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses Development

The theoretical model promoting this study is presented in Fig. 1. This model demonstrates how SM affect employees' motivation and knowledge, performance as well as their impact on intention in organization system.

Figure -1: Proposed research model

2.1. Social Media and motivation

According to the theory of SDT, the initial factor of motivation is perceived autonomy which indicates to users' understandings of the scope to which they are advised to exercise certain system, or given independence to trial with system attributes (14). Staff members of the institute require the awareness of autonomy to intentional on modern system attributes (14). The source of the usage examples is the urge for autonomy among users, which is described as excitement to self-regulate their assurance to develop performance. Furthermore, there has been some encouraging evidence that management support, desires, and motivation are key conduct markers in terms of user ability(15). According to SDT theory, expanding one's capacities is a huge element for the view of ability(16). SM research uncovers that administration expands the feeling of relatedness between users in different manners, for instance by supporting connections among managers and officials or by encouraging systems administration and building relations among different colleagues of different specialty units (17). SDT places the view of relatedness is convincingly dependent on a feeling of

conceitedness to other people(18,19). Social networking is an exceptionally multifaceted, interrelate and multifunctional apparatus that requires associations between framework information and workers put in different specialty units (20). This basic boost and motivate employees to help one another. These skill of relations SM users are externally synchronized, in view of incentives or penalty, modify their amount of effort according to the organizational agenda. This suggests discipline and reward are critical for motivating components, advancing positive practices (16,18). As a result, we could hypothesize that:

Hypothesis -1. There are positive influences of social media on employees' motivation.

2.2. Social Media and Knowledge Management

Workers may not be aware of the knowledge they possess that is valuable to the company, they may lack the motivation to share this expertise, and there may be no mechanisms in place for them to do so. SM presents a encouraging arrangement of devices for bunch coordinated effort, giving incorporated stages to correspondence, cooperation, and knowledge exchange(21) and hence gives a valuable system to knowledge creation and spread (22), and sharing (23). SM encourages knowledge sharing by expanding knowledge reuse by representatives and by arranging of the dependence on inflexible authoritative arrangements. Online network gatherings and sites make immediate responses circles as beneficiaries of knowledge can impart their responses continuously to react with different users and again, getting explanation or new information to assist them with conquering knowledge limits (24). Thus, SM can make an organization fit for supporting professionals in knowledge sharing, possibly filling inconsistency of abilities, proficiency and knowledge inside the institute (25). Therefore, we can hypothesize that:

Hypothesis -2. There are positive influences of social media on employees' knowledge management.

2.3. Social Media and Employees Performance

Putting time and resources in social networks causes facilitates workers to accumulate standards of correspondence and shared trust between colleagues that gets essential and supportive whereas taking part in synergistic actions (conceptualizing or critical thinking in groups). Additionally, it improves task execution in cross-useful groups where individuals with various abilities group assets to meet up the shared and ordinary objective of the responsibility. Whereas social resources (SM) highlights on singular worker's life fulfillment; relational social resources estimates the degree of trust between representatives and behavioral social resources indicates to the degree of individual representative's support in community and political actions (26). Past studies have discovered that human resources who use social networks (like Facebook and Twitter) are bound to believe better levels of fulfillment, joy, and likeness (27). This shows worker contribution in organization with social systems in administration actions may have huge positive effect on the interpersonal area. Hence, we can hypothesize that:

Hypothesis -3. There are positive influences of social media on employees' performance.

2.4. Social Media and Intention.

According to SDT (motivational) theory, there are some factors (extrinsic and intrinsic factors) which influence users' intention to contribute in organization using SM (28). Kaplan and Haenlein, (2010) stated, with the help of SM, users can creating content to support their important liability (29). Earlier studies have specified that "user created content as item studies, can support with advancing transactions" (30,31). The education or information provided by SM are considered to be better dependable(30), and increase the knowledge notability in the brains of users(31). While there is plentiful sharing of information through a system or services there might build users' responsiveness and make users better skilled about the system for their applying alternatives and hence these leading better deals (32). Moreover, the effect of application output on sustained intention to use SM applications will be stronger for employees or management authorities high on uncertainty avoidance. Those individuals, who are self-motivated, have shortage of knowledge will accept technical terminology (SM) and these will be driving them to continued intention. Furthermore, SM affect peoples' intention to participate in using a new system in the workplace. Hence, in organizations SM can enhance discussions, sharing knowledge (33) and reducing barriers to sharing knowledge within organizations (34) between coworkers and management authorities and up lifting positive influence on EP. Hence, we can hypothesize:

Hypothesis- 4: Motivation has positive impacts of on employees' intentions.

Hypothesis- 5: Knowledge management has positive impacts of on employees' intentions.

Hypothesis- 6: Employees' performance has positive impacts of on employees' intentions.

Hypothesis- 7: Social media has positive influence of on employees' intentions.

2.5. Moderating effect of Motivation, Knowledge management, Employees Performance

Organizational performance could directly or indirectly affected by SM resources through employees communications and with other resources or capabilities (35). In the role of HRM managements' processes for intentional purposes also allowed opportunities for managements to develop social networks in the organization(36). Hence, KM process based on organizational potentialities, which rely on the use of information system resources for better performance. These arguments suggest that KM mediates in the relationship between SM and in their intention. On the other hand, motivation and EP allow organizations to develop their business process (36,37). Thus, motivation, KM and EP are anticipated as a mediator in the relationship between SM and in their intention. We can hypothesize the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis-8: Motivation mediates the relationship between social media and users' intentions.

Hypothesis-9: Knowledge Management mediates the relationship between social media and users' intentions.

Hypothesis-10: Employees Performance mediates the relationship between social media and users' intentions.

3. Materials and methods

In this segment, we focus on the experimental analysis. With regard to presented literature review, we established a questionnaire for the survey. Here we illustrated the questionnaire with demographic followed by main questions. After data collection, we presented data analysis methods for the survey.

3.1. Questionnaire design

To accomplish the principle objectives of the survey, the questionnaire was used as a major instrument to collect data with regards to the independent variables; SM and the dependent variables motivation (Intrinsic motivation and Extrinsic motivation) KM , EP , and intentions. The survey's topic was based on a body of literature that was used to create the questionnaire. Using a seven-point Likert-type response format (i.e. "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (7)), a structured questionnaire is constructed. It is necessary to use constructs that have already been studied in order to maintain objectivity. Specifically, the items SM modified from Wamba, S.F., et al., (2017) (28); the dependent variables motivation (Intrinsic motivation and Extrinsic motivation) adapted as well as modified from Rezvani, A., Khosravi, P., & Dong, L. (2017) (38); KM and EP adapted from Abualoush, S. H. et al (2018) (39) and intentions adapted and modified from Yong, D., M. Akter, (2020) (40). The constructs substance and their resources are shown in Table 1.

Table-1: Convergent validity of measurement model.

ITEMS	Loading	α	AVE	CR
Social Media (SM) (41)				
SM 1	0.861			
SM 2	0.791	0.851	0.615	0.892
SM 3	0.799			
SM 4	0.753			
MO: Internic Motivation (IM) (42)				
IM 1	0.801			
IM 2	0.754			
IM 3	0.721	0.827	0.595	0.856
IM 4	0.719			
IM 5	0.701			
MO: Externic Motivation (EM)				
EM 1	0.754			
EM 2	0.721	0.879	.601	0.841
EM 3	0.701			
Knowledge Management (KM) (43)				
KM 1	0.898			
KM 4	0.867	0.901	0.621	0.882
KM 7	0.855			
KM 5	0.852			
KM 2	0.776			
KM 6	0.752			
KM 8	0.720			
KM 3	0.712			
KM 9	0.710			
Employees Performance (EP) (43)				
EP 9	0.901			

EP 5	0.891			
EP 1	0.806			
EP 10	0.803			
EP 6	0.802			
EP 7	0.791			
EP 3	0.789	0.798	0.632	0.829
EP 4	0.786			
EP 11	0.765			
EP 2	0.757			
EP 12	0.711			
EP 8	0.701			
Intentions (IN) (44)				
IN 1	0.867			
IN2	0.798	0.815	0.617	0.901
IN 3	0.771			
IN 4	0.703			

3.2. Sample population and data collection

We did some preliminary work before starting the main study. First, we unified a group of people, which contains few Master's and Ph.D. students with specialized skills in survey design. Second, by the group's suggestions critical and minor changes have done with regarding to the sequence and word. Finally, we sent out 30 surveys in order to get feedback. We were able to check the final form of the survey after going through all of the responses. Mail and SM were used to collect the data, which came from major Vietnamese cities such as Can Tho, Da Nang, Haiphong and Ho Chi Minh City. The main target population were included those who are official stuff of different government and nongovernment companies. Within 2 months, we reminded the official stuff and in SM to fill the questionnaire. Our target respondents' age groups were between 18 to 51+ years old; because these groups of people are main user at the same time adopters of new technology (SM). After completing the survey, participants were given a gift. 25 of the 374 surveys were discarded due to missing data, leaving 349 for use in the final study assessment. Demographic materials are in Table - 2.

Table-2: Descriptive statistics of respondents' characteristics.

Measures	Items	Frequency	(%)
Gender	Male	188	53.9%
	Female	169	45.5%
Age	≤18-20	92	26.4%
	21-30	127	36.4%
	31-40	96	27.5%
	41-50	34	6.6%
	51+	11	3.1%
	Education	High School/ Diploma	69
Bachelors		171	49.0%
Masters		109	32.2%
General employee		154	44.1%
Position	Low level management	106	30.4%
	Middle level management	69	19.8%
	Department manager	20	5.7%
	<1 year	52	14.9%

Work experience	1-5 years	209	59.9%
	6-10 years	49	14.0%
	≥11 years	39	11.2%
Department function	Production	40	11.5%
	Human resource	28	8.0%
	Account & Finance	36	10.3%
	IT management	58	16.6%
	Administration	62	17.8%
	Marketing and sales	81	23.2%
	Support and service	44	12.6%

3.3. Evaluation method

To assess the structural model, we employed a partial least squares (PLS) method based on structural equation modeling (SEM). According to Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, and Mena, (2017) (45) PLS is a second-generation technique that combines regression and component factor analysis to simultaneously analyze the measurement and structural model (CFA). The Smart-PLS 3.2.8 software was utilized in this work to do a PLS estimation.

4. Analysis results

4.1. Common method bias

For the social research common method bias is the concerning issue. Hence, we calculated common method bias with the help of the variance inflation factor (VIF) (46). In the PLS-SEM the results of VIT should be less than or equal 3.3; and in this study the value of VIF is between 1.88 and 2.49. Therefore, in our study there is no serious issue of common method bias.

4.2. Measurement model

First of all, check the reliability as well as validity of those constructs which were used for the study. We also performed internal consistency, convergent validity and discriminate validity (47). We assessed above validities by analyzing Cronbach's alpha (α), factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). All constructs had CR values greater than 0.8 and AVE values greater than 0.5. As a result, a reasonable converging validity found in this study (Table-1). If the construct measurements differ from those of other constructs, the discriminant validity will validate that fact (47,48). To demonstrate reasonable discriminant validity, construct square root of AVEs where all of them were higher than correlation between variables (table-3).

Table-3: Measurement model and discriminant validity.

	Mean	SD	SM	MO	KW	EP	IN
Social Media (SM)	3.88	0.95	0.851				
Motivation (MO)	3.52	1.05	0.196	0.847			
Knowledge (KW)	3.26	0.85	0.359	0.336	0.790		
Employees Performance (EP)	3.57	1.01	0.267	0.571	0.432	0.856	
Intention (IN)	3.31	0.81	0.321	0.247	0.178	0.343	0.819

4.3. Structural model

The results of the study model show in Fig. 2. We test the estimated path of coefficients of the structural model and assess our hypotheses. According to the PLS statistic for structural model (shown in Figure-2), there has a positive effect between SM and users' motivation, KM, in the organization cultures, supporting H1 ($\beta=0.356$, $p < 0.001$) and H2 ($\beta=0.391$, $p < 0.001$). On the other hand, there has no significance effects between SM and the EP supporting H3 ($\beta=0.121$, $p < 0.62$) i.e. the hypothesis is not accepted.

Figure -2: Results of the research model

In addition, motivation, KM, EP and SM have positive effects on employees' intention in the organization cultures, supporting H4 ($\beta=0.331$, $p < 0.001$); H5 ($\beta=0.278$, $p < 0.01$); H6 ($\beta=0.239$, $p < 0.01$) and H7 ($\beta=0.259$, $p < 0.001$). Finally, as for the mediating effect, the bootstrapping results show that the normalized indirect effect of SM on employees' motivation, KM and the EP have positive influences in the organization cultures supporting with H8 ($\beta=0.139$, $p < 0.05$); H9 ($\beta=0.156$, $p < 0.05$) and H10 ($\beta=0.186$, $p < 0.01$). According to Hair et al. (2017) (45) the value of R^2 should be above 0.2; because, in behavioral research the value should be above than 0.2 is considered as relative and acceptable. In this study, the $R^2 = 0.519$ for employees' intention.

Table 4: Structural model results (hypothesis testing).

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	Std. error	t-value	Decision	R ²
H1	SM→MO	0.356	0.035	7.695***	Supported	
H2	SM→KW	0.391	0.045	7.926***	Supported	
H3	SM→EP	0.121	0.012	1.153 ^{ns}	Not-Supported	
H4	MO→IN	0.331	0.061	6.775***	Supported	
H5	KW→IN	0.278	0.039	3.902**	Supported	0.519
H6	EP→IN	0.239	0.025	3.612**	Supported	
H7	SM→IN	0.259	0.065	4.534***	Supported	
Interactions						
H8	SM→MO→IN	0.139	0.049	2.001*	Supported	
H9	SM→KW→IN	0.156	0.051	1.981*	Supported	
H10	SM→EP→IN	0.186	0.053	2.514**	Supported	

5. Discussion and implications

5.1. Discussion

This analysis intends to incorporate SDT(motivation) theory (19) and inspect the impact of SM usage on employees' empowerment. The outcomes uncover some absorbing findings. First of all, the results illustrate that the usage of SM positively influences Intrinsic as well as extrinsic motivation. Representing that, through SM employee can maintain relationships with co-worker and friends. We have found significant relationships between workers' use of SM and motivation. This is reliable with the finding of the investigation of Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw's, (2010) (49) that, SM shapes relationships with motivation. Moreover, we have found that intrinsic motivation is definitely identified with helpfulness of the system. This finding is in opposition of Sorebo et al. (2009) (50), who tried this relationship about e-learning use. This study similarly draws out with the SM model to represent the function of motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic). Besides, our findings have explained how SM rouses influences employees in an unexpected way. The outcomes support Rezvani, A., Khosravi, P., & Dong, L. (2017); (38) findings identified with the function of social media in affecting motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic). Our findings show that, motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic) traces employees aims to persistently draw in with the system, which is dependable with researchers' finding that, SM have constructive outcome on client extrinsic motivation (51). The consequences of our study model propose that diverse SM stage distinguishably affect various elements of motivation (intrinsic and extrinsic); that means there is a solid relationship between SM to fulfilling employees' motivation, to motivating employees extrinsically.

Our second study hypothesis's result are also positive. Here we found a significant relationship between SM and employees' KM which results have the same opinion with the earlier studies (52). That means, in the achievement of the organizational goal KM plays a vital role. This study also concurs with the study of Khodabakhshi, F., N.K. Sajad, and M. Shiargar, (2013) (53) this study shows that social media and employee cooperation promote knowledge management and allow employees to gain new information and abilities. The findings of Somayyeh, S. and P. Morteza, also support this conclusion (54), where the statistic shows, the relation among social media, knowledge management intention. There the authors illustrated that by using SM the employees could carry out their duties with the help of KM, skills and abilities to accomplish the goals of the organization. In addition our study outcomes agrees with the study of Fardin, (2012) (55) and the study of Harandi and Motlagh, (2014) (56). The all authors assured that, SM directly impact for the dimensions of KM. We also found that, the advanced use of SM with KM provides better performance where the communication among the employees assists in solving occupational difficulties.

This study analysis shows that, there is positive impact between SM and EP, but is not strong enough to support this hypothesis. The reason may occurred by the fact that, companies use systems are traditional to accomplish the daily custom work. Obviously, this not reflect in reaching the requisite efficiency, and this may be because the company follows advancements in the information systems, particularly the tools for analyzing data, which assist the staff to perform their work professionally. Innovating and gathering

information about their work environment are made easier by these tools. Abu Kareem, (2013) (57) also found that the results do not match. Management information systems should be geared at boosting efficiency and effectiveness in the workplace by aligning themselves with modern technology, as well as the organizations' administrative rules. According to Ahrabi and Darestani, (2014) (58) there is a good correlation between the usage of current information systems and employee performance, as well as the ability of managers to swiftly access information about the financial performance of a firm that utilizes these systems. As a result, not only are employees happier, but their productivity rises above that of firms without sophisticated information systems. Our data also shows that SM and the users' intentions have a substantial impact.

From the mediation tests, we observed that motivation, KM and employees' performance mediate the relation between SM and employees' intention (p-value < 0.000 for the three effects). Therefore, all three proposed mediation effects are positive impact and significant. However, our study found that EP are not affected by SM but its' has positive impact in the mediating of SM and intentional behavior of the employees. This agrees with the earlier studies (59). Because, of the use of SM, employees will be able to gather, share, discuss, and make decisions with their coworkers on their own, allowing them to operate more efficiently and effectively. This validates the findings of an earlier study (60).

5.2. Theoretical implications

The research outcomes have the following theoretical implication. First, this study draws our attention to the necessity of considering the role of social media, and determinants of STD (motivation), knowledge and EP in between employees' intention. Second, we find that motivation, KM and EP mediate the relationship between SM and employees' intention. SM can help us to collect better knowledge and could improve our motivation and performance as well as effects on intention.

5.3. Practical implications

There are some practical applications from this research, which may derive from the preceding analysis. First, this study clearly tells managers which determinants of SM will develop employees' knowledge and how does its' improve employees' motivation and performance in the work place to develop better intention. Using these employees could improve the level of interactions to develop superior trust and hence can improve adoption intention. For example, employees can bring the sociability with others through SM. Second, this study short-cuts management's attention to the regular use of SM within the firm. Researchers' findings show that organizations' willingness and ability to create and share new knowledge are positively correlated when it comes to using SM. As a result, employees are increasingly using new technologies in the workplace for self-improvement or ongoing group learning (61).

IT managers or policy makers should squeeze their idea of networking adoption intention through SM with a careful control where proper usage of SM could be able to bring optimistic organizational outcomes. Third, this research gives confidence to the employees that, SM guide in knowledge management processes. Usually in organizations, employees are obtaining knowledge through contributing and retrieving from their bases or superiors. In this study, SM is a bottom-up, unofficial, individual and intentional approach that complements conventional knowledge management processes. Particularly, when SM and knowledge are both in place, organizations can consider introducing both SM and KM systems concurrently to improve organizational learning. Hence, managers must treat SM usage as their booster of KM. Finally, organization managers must pay attention to actions, which generate and share knowledge to support and improve personal performance to enhance organizational goals. This concept will help organizations to the potential long-term benefits of technology investment.

5.4. Limitations and future work

Like all other studies, this study also has some limitations. First, data was collected from major cities; hence, future research needs to use the data from all districts. Second, it is also important to note that all of the variables in this study were measured at the same time. The long-term technique may be used in future investigations to verify the findings. Third, the target population for this study was the people 18 to 51+ years of age. Future studies can target people with other age groups to get ample knowledge of employees' SM adoption intention. This survey was limited within Vietnamese; after this, there may be a cultural barrier to overcome. Future research may be able to simplify or change the study model by conducting empirical work in diverse cultural contexts. Because of this, the findings of this study should be interpreted with caution. Finally, this investigation is confined to the intent. Studies of actual behavior and other variables that explain discrepancies between intentions and actions may be the subject of future research.

6. Conclusion

Popularity of SM and growing number of organizations are integrating SM in their organizations to support communication and cooperation. However, study on SM in the work context is rare for the lower developing countries. To investigate the influence of SM in the workplace and the underlying mechanism for how they create value on employees' motivation, knowledge and their performance at work place we have developed a model through incorporating SM with SDT theory. As we show, SM can encourage and develop of employees' motivation, knowledge by network ties that, in turn, can facilitate knowledge transfer and develop performance. Both SM and KM include significantly in working performance. We calculate SM's benefits for organizations, providing employees as well as managers' motivation to organize them in the organizations with optimistic expectation. By the strategy offered in this study, organizations could possibly enhance employees' work performance through SM.

References

1. Mohapatra S, Priyanka V, Kohli I, Mishra RJIJoA, Sciences S. Impact of corona virus COVID-19 on the global economy. 2020;771-8.
2. JUNG K-J, JEON B-HJJoDS. The Negative Effect of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Acceleration of Startup Innovation in the Retail Supply Chain. 2021;19(9):79-90.
3. Elphinston RA, Noller P. Time to Face It! Facebook Intrusion and the Implications for Romantic Jealousy and Relationship Satisfaction. *Cyberpsychology Behavior & Social Networking*. 2011;14(11):631.
4. Porter K, Mitchell J, Grace M, Shinosky S, Gordon V. A Study of the Effects of Social Media Use and Addiction on Relationship Satisfaction. *South African Geographical Journal Bng A Record of the Proceedings of the South African Geographical Society*. 2012;79(2):147-52.
5. Thomas KJ, Akdere M. Social Media as Collaborative Media in Workplace Learning. *Human resource development review*. 2013;12(3):329-44.
6. Majchrzak A, Faraj S, Kane GC, Azad B. The Contradictory Influence of Social Media Affordances on Online Communal Knowledge Sharing. *Journal of Computer-mediated Communication*. 19(1):38–55.
7. Fulk J, Yuan YC. Location, Motivation, and Social Capitalization via Enterprise Social Networking. *Journal of Computer-mediated Communication*. 2013;19(1):20-37.
8. Andriole, Stephen J. Business impact of Web 2.0 technologies. *Communications of the ACM*. 2010;53(12):67.
9. Razmerita L, Kirchner K, Nabeth T. Social Media in Organizations: Leveraging Personal and Collective Knowledge Processes. *Journal of Organizational Computing & Electronic Commerce*. 2014;24(1):74-93.
10. Alavi M, Leidner DE. REVIEW: KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS: CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS AND RESEARCH ISSUES. *MIS quarterly*. 2001;25(1):p.107-36.
11. Ma WWK, Chan A. Knowledge sharing and social media: Altruism, perceived online attachment motivation, and perceived online relationship commitment. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 2014;39(oct.):51-8.
12. Hasan M, Zhou SN. Knowledge management in global organisations. *International Business Research*. 2015;8(6):165-73.
13. Masa'deh Re, Shannak R, Maqableh M, Tarhini A. The impact of knowledge management on job performance in higher education. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*. 2017.
14. Ahuja MK, Thatcher JB. Moving beyond intentions and toward the theory of trying: effects of work environment and gender on post-adoption information technology use. *MIS quarterly*. 2005;29(3):427-59.

15. Mitchell JI, Gagné M, Beaudry A, Dyer L. The role of perceived organizational support, distributive justice and motivation in reactions to new information technology. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 2012;28(2):729-38.
16. Deci EL, Ryan RM. Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. *Canadian psychology/Psychologie canadienne*. 2008;49(3):182.
17. Ke W, Wei KK. Organizational culture and leadership in ERP implementation. *Decision support systems*. 2008;45(2):208-18.
18. Olafsen AH, Halvari H, Forest J, Deci EL. Show them the money? The role of pay, managerial need support, and justice in a self-determination theory model of intrinsic work motivation. *Scandinavian journal of psychology*. 2015;56(4):447-57.
19. Deci EL, Ryan RM. The " what " and " why " of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological inquiry*. 2000;11(4):227-68.
20. Xue Y, Liang H, Wu L. Punishment, justice, and compliance in mandatory IT settings. *Information Systems Research*. 2011;22(2):400-14.
21. Al-Busaidi KA. SWOT of social networking sites for group work in government organizations. *VINE: The journal of information and knowledge management systems*. 2014.
22. Von Krogh G. How does social software change knowledge management? Toward a strategic research agenda. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*. 2012;21(2):154-64.
23. Schiuma G, Vuori V, Okkonen J. Knowledge sharing motivational factors of using an intra-organizational social media platform. *Journal of knowledge management*. 2012.
24. Yates D, Paquette S. Emergency knowledge management and social media technologies: A case study of the 2010 Haitian earthquake. *International journal of information management*. 2011;31(1):6-13.
25. Alberghini E, Cricelli L, Grimaldi M. A methodology to manage and monitor social media inside a company: a case study. *Journal of Knowledge Management*. 2014.
26. Scheufele DA, Shah DV. Personality strength and social capital: The role of dispositional and informational variables in the production of civic participation. *Communication research*. 2000;27(2):107-31.
27. Peter J, Valkenburg PM, Schouten AP. Characteristics and motives of adolescents talking with strangers on the Internet. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*. 2006;9(5):526-30.
28. Wamba SF, Bhattacharya M, Trinchera L, Ngai EW. Role of intrinsic and extrinsic factors in user social media acceptance within workspace: Assessing unobserved heterogeneity. *International Journal of Information Management*. 2017;37(2):1-13.
29. Kaplan, A. M, Haenlein, M. *Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media*. Business Horizons Bloomington. 2010.
30. Brown JO, Broderick AJ, Lee N. Word of mouth communication within online communities: Conceptualizing the online social network. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*. 2007;21(3):2-20.

31. Forman C, Wiesenfeld GB. The Interplay Between Digital and Social Networks || Examining the Relationship Between Reviews and Sales: The Role of Reviewer Identity Disclosure in Electronic Markets. *Information Systems Research*. 2008;19(3):291-313.
32. Godes D, Mayzlin D. Using Online Conversations to Study Word-of-Mouth Communication. *Marketing Science*. 2004;23(4):545-60.
33. Majchrzak A, Faraj S, Kane GC, Azad B. The contradictory influence of social media affordances on online communal knowledge sharing. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*. 2013;19(1):38-55.
34. Leonardi PM. Social media, knowledge sharing, and innovation: Toward a theory of communication visibility. *Information systems research*. 2014;25(4):796-816.
35. Wade MR, Hulland J. The Resource-Based View and Information Systems Research: Review, Extension, and Suggestions for Future Research. *MIS Quarterly*. 2004;28(1):107-42.
36. Melville N, Kraemer K, Gurbaxani V. Review: information technology and organizational performance: an integrative model of it business value: Society for Information Management and The Management Information Systems Research Center; 2004.
37. Chen Y, Wang Y, Nevo S, Jin J, Wang L, Chow WS. IT capability and organizational performance: the roles of business process agility and environmental factors. *European Journal of Information Systems*. 2014;23(3):326-42.
38. Rezvani A, Khosravi P, Dong L. Motivating users toward continued usage of information systems: Self-determination theory perspective. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 2017;76:263-75.
39. Abualoush SH, Obeidat AM, Tarhini A, Al-Badi A. The role of employees' empowerment as an intermediary variable between knowledge management and information systems on employees' performance. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*. 2018.
40. Yong D, Akter M, Rahman MM. Influence of Trust and social presence in m-commerce adoption intention in Bangladesh: An empirical study. *North American Academic Research*. 2020.
41. Wamba SF, Bhattacharya M, Trinchera L, Ngai EWJJoIM. Role of intrinsic and extrinsic factors in user social media acceptance within workspace: Assessing unobserved heterogeneity. 2017;37(2):1-13.
42. Rezvani A, Khosravi P, Dong LJCiHB. Motivating users toward continued usage of information systems: Self-determination theory perspective. 2017;76:263-75.
43. Abualoush SH, Obeidat AM, Tarhini A, Al-Badi AJVJoI, Systems KM. The role of employees' empowerment as an intermediary variable between knowledge management and information systems on employees' performance. 2018.
44. Ding Y, Akter M, Rahman MMJNAAR. Influence of trust and social presence in mcommerce adoption intention in Bangladesh: an empirical study. 2019;2(12):232-48.
45. Hair Jr JF, Sarstedt M, Ringle CM, Gudergan SP. *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling*: Sage Publications; 2017.

46. Kock N. Common method bias in PLS-SEM: A full collinearity assessment approach. *International Journal of e-Collaboration (IJeC)*. 2015;11(4):1-10.
47. Hair JF, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing theory and Practice*. 2011;19(2):139-52.
48. Jiang C, Rashid RM, Wang J. Investigating the role of social presence dimensions and information support on consumers' trust and shopping intentions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 2019;51:263-70.
49. Davis FD, Bagozzi RP, Warshaw PR. Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation to Use Computers in the Workplace1. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*. 2010;22(14):1111-32.
50. Sorebo O, Halvari H, Gulli VF, Kristiansen R. The role of self-determination theory in explaining teachers' motivation to continue to use e-learning technology. *Computers & Education*. 2009;53(4):1177-87.
51. UĞUR NG, BAŞAK B. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations of Social Media Use: College Students Perspective. *The Online Journal of Quality in Higher Education-July*. 2018;5(3).
52. Bharati P, Zhang W, Chaudhury A. Better knowledge with social media? Exploring the roles of social capital and organizational knowledge management. *Journal of Knowledge Management*. 2015.
53. Khodabakhshi F, Sajad NK, Shiargar M. The impact of knowledge management on innovation with the mediating role of empowerment. 2013.
54. Somayyeh S, Morteza P. Investigation the role of knowledge management in staff empowerment (Case study: general department of education, Western Azerbaijan province). *International Journal of Review in Life Sciences*. 2015;5(4):163-8.
55. Fardin H. Evaluation of empowerment of human resources and effectiveness. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*. 2012;2(10):9998-10006.
56. Harandi M, Motlagh A. Studying the relationship between knowledge management and employee empowerment, case study. *Computer Research Center of Islamic Sciences*. 2014;2(3):221-8.
57. Kareem A, Ahmed AM. The Relationship of Management Information Systems to Improving Administrative Performance-A Field Study on Application to NGOs in the Gaza Strip: Master Thesis (unpublished), Faculty of Economics and Administrative ...; 2013.
58. Ahrabi SZ, Darestani SA. Studying the role of management information systems in improving organizational performance (Case study: National oil rich regions company). *International Academic Journal of Business Management*. 2016;3(10):1-11.
59. Nzuve SNM, Bakari TH. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPOWERMENT AND PERFORMANCE IN THE CITY COUNCIL OF NAIROBI. *Problems of Management in Century*. 2012.
60. Shih WL, Tsai CY. The effects of knowledge management capabilities on perceived school effectiveness in career and technical education. *Journal of Knowledge Management*. 2016;20(6):1373-92.

61. Qi C, Chau PYK. Will enterprise social networking systems promote knowledge management and organizational learning? An empirical study. *Journal of Organizational Computing and Electronic Commerce*. 2018;28(1):31-57.

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